

Potential Antineoplastic Agents : Synthetic and Pharmacological Studies on Some N-Aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazolyl)thiocarbamides

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Manuscript received 11 August 1981, accepted 2 February 1982

A number of compounds belonging to the series N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides have been synthesized by the condensation of corresponding 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles with different arylisothiocyanates respectively with a view to test their antitumor activity. The preliminary pharmacological investigations on the compounds have also been carried out.

DURING the last few years, there has been a growing interest in the synthesis and biological evaluation of compounds containing the N*-N*-S* or O*-N*-S* tridentate ligand system¹⁻⁵ or arylazogrouping^{6,7}. This interest stems mainly from certain interesting biological activities^{8,9}, carcinostatic activities of heterocyclic carboxyl-aldehyde thiosemicarbazones and the interfering action of 5-arylazopyrimidines with nucleic acid synthesis. Moreover, various Schiff bases from benzaldehyde, nitrogenmustards and thiazoleamines have been reported to possess antitumor activity¹⁰⁻¹². As a part of a general study directed towards the development of antineoplastic agents¹³, the above rationale led to the examination of the synthesis and biological properties of N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides having N*-N*-S* ligand system, arylazogrouping and a modified azomethine linkage¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-*o*-chlorophenylazothiazolyl)-, N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-*m*-chlorophenylazothiazolyl)-, and N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-*p*-chlorophenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides by the condensation of the corresponding 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles with appropriate arylisothiocyanates.

The precursor 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole was obtained by the condensation of acetophenone with thiourea in presence of iodine¹⁷. The arylazogroup at C-5 was introduced by the coupling of different diazonium salts.

On boiling equimolar quantities of arylisothiocyanates¹⁸ and 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles in benzene on a steam bath, high yields of

the corresponding N-aryl-N'-2[4-phenyl-5-(*o*, *m*, *p*-chlorophenyl)azothiazolyl]thiocarbamides (Table 1) were obtained. Purification was achieved by recrystallization with DMF-ethanol (1 : 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained using KBr pellets and a Perkin-Elmer 720 Infracord spectrophotometer; bands reported were atleast of medium intensity. The results of elemental analyses were in good agreement with those of theoretical values.

2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole : It was prepared according to the method in the literature¹⁷.

*2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-*o*-chlorophenylazothiazole* : Sodium nitrite (1.4 g; 0.02 mole) dissolved in water (25 ml) was gradually added to a well cooled solution of 2-chloroaniline (2.55 g; 0.02 mole) in 3 N HCl (2.5 ml). The diazonium salt solution was filtered in to a cold suspension of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (3.52 g; 0.02 mole) and sodium acetate (5 g) in ethanol (50 ml). After 2 hr, 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-*o*-chlorophenylazothiazole was filtered and washed several times with water. It was recrystallized as orange red needles from DMF-ethanol mixture (1 : 1), yield 4.70 g (75%), m.p. 215°.

*2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-*m*-chlorophenylazothiazole* and *2-amino-4-phenyl-5-*p*-chlorophenylazothiazole* were also prepared by adopting a similar procedure.

*N-phenyl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-*o*-chlorophenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamide* : A mixture of phenylisothiocyanate (1.35 g; 0.01 mole) and 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-*o*-chlorophenylazothiazole (3.14 g; 0.01

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mole) in benzene (15 ml) was refluxed for 6-8 hr on a steam bath. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (40-60°). The crude thiocarbamide thus obtained was crystallized from DMF-ethanol mixture (1:1) as deep red needles, 3.77 g (84%), m.p. 199°. Anal. Found: C, 58.71; H, 3.53; N, 15.54; S, 14.21. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₆ClN₂S₂: C, 58.73; H, 3.56; N, 15.57; S, 14.23%.

Similarly, other N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-o-chlorophenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides were prepared by the condensation of 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-o-chlorophenylazothiazole with different arylisothiocyanates.

Using similar procedure as above several viz., N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-m-chlorophenylazothiazolyl)

thiocarbamides and N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-p-chlorophenylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides (Table 1) were obtained.

These N-aryl-N'-2(4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazolyl) thiocarbamides were characterized on the basis of their elemental analyses and the presence of characteristic bands N=N (1615 cm⁻¹), NH (3400 cm⁻¹), N=C=S (1520 cm⁻¹) and substituted benzene ring (760 cm⁻¹) in their ir spectra.

Biological results :

In L-1210 leukemia, BDF₁ mice were inoculated intraperitoneally with 10⁶ tumor cells. The index of evaluation for the ascitic tumor is T/C [(mean survival time of treated mice/mean survival time of control mice) × 100]. For L-1210, a T/C ≥ 125 is considered positive. The finely ground drugs were suspended in a solution of sterile distilled water with a drop of Tween-80. The drugs were given daily intraperitoneally at approximately the maximum tolerated doses, starting 24 hr after tumor inoculation. The detailed methods for the evaluation of antitumor activity in mice have been described elsewhere¹⁹⁻²¹.

Shown in Table 1 are the data of antitumor activity against L-1210 leukemia. It appears from this primary screening that the level of toxicity varied greatly in this group. Although all the compounds were found to be practically inactive, some compounds viz. Nos. 5, 10, 16, 20, 26 and 30 were somewhat more potent than the other members of this series.

TABLE 1—SYNTHETIC AND PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF N-ARYL-N'-2(4-PHENYL-5-ARYLAZOTHIAZOLYL) THIOCARBAMIDES AGAINST L-1210 LYMPHOID LEUKEMIA ASCITIC FLUID IMPLANTED INTRAPERITONEALLY IN BDF₁ MICE

Sl. No.	Compound* R'	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Survivors ⁺	T/C ⁺⁺ %
1.	2-Cl	H	84	199	6/6	101
2.	"	2-CH ₃	81	190	3/6	94
3.	"	3-CH ₃	72	210	5/6	95
4.	"	4-CH ₃	76	207	4/6	92
5.	"	2-OCH ₃	82	216	5/6	103
6.	"	4-OCH ₃	80	230	6/6	90
7.	"	2-Cl	78	227	4/6	95
8.	"	3-Cl	75	235	3/6	98
9.	"	4-Cl	74	212	6/6	102
10.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	72	239	2/6	104
11.	3-Cl	H	88	240	5/6	100
12.	"	2-CH ₃	80	249	6/6	88
13.	"	3-CH ₃	82	230	5/6	96
14.	"	4-CH ₃	85	256	4/6	102
15.	"	2-OCH ₃	80	268	6/6	100
16.	"	4-OCH ₃	84	262	4/6	105
17.	"	2-Cl	80	238	4/6	90
18.	"	3-Cl	78	245	5/6	95
19.	"	4-Cl	82	254	5/6	103
20.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	85	233	6/6	107
21.	4-Cl	H	85	250	4/6	99
22.	"	2-CH ₃	83	236	5/6	88
23.	"	3-CH ₃	78	244	6/6	94
24.	"	4-CH ₃	80	260	6/6	100
25.	"	2-OCH ₃	82	275	6/6	96
26.	"	4-OCH ₃	88	281	5/6	106
27.	"	2-Cl	85	292	4/6	98
28.	"	3-Cl	74	240	6/6	92
29.	"	4-Cl	80	231	3/6	101
30.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	78	258	5/6	104

* Analytical results for C, H, N and S for these compounds agreed within ± 0.5% of the theoretical values.

+ All doses for these compounds were 400 mg/kg.

++ Ratio of mean survival time of test animals (T) to control (C). Mean survival time of control is 30 days.

References

1. R. W. BROCKMAN, J. R. THOMSON, M. J. BELL and H. E. SKIFFER, *Cancer Res.*, 1956, **16**, 167.
2. F. A. FRENCH and B. L. FREEDLANDER, *Cancer Res.*, 1958, **18**, 1920.
3. F. A. FRENCH and B. L. FREEDLANDER, *Cancer Res.*, 1960, **20**, 505.
4. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, JR., *Cancer Res.*, 1963, **23**, 9.
5. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, JR., *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 585.
6. E. J. MODEST, H. N. SCHLEIN and G. E. FOLEY, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1957, **9**, 68.
7. R. E. HARMON, F. E. DUTTON and H. D. WARREN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 627.
8. D. J. BEAVER, D. P. ROMAN and P. J. STOFFEL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 501.
9. R. L. MAYER, P. C. EISMAN and E. A. KONOPKA, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1953, **82**, 769.
10. S. S. SABNIS and K. D. KULRAMI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 447.
11. F. D. POPP and W. KIRSCH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 3858.
12. M. G. DHAPALAPUR, S. S. SABNIS and C. V. DELIWALA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 154.
13. H. G. GARG and R. A. SHARMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, **12**, 1123.
14. J. S. UPADHYAYA and W. U. MALIK, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1980, **42**, 88.

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15. J. S. UPADHYAYA and P. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981 (In Press).
16. J. S. UPADHYAYA and P. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 792.
17. R. M. DODSON and L. C. KING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242.
18. F. B. DAINS, R. Q. BREWSTER and C. P. OLANDER, *Org. Synth. Coll.*, **1**, 447.
19. R. I. GERAN, N. H. GREENBERG, M. M. MACDONALD, A. M. SCHUMACHER and B. J. ABBOTT, *Cancer Chemother. Rept. part 3*, 1972, **3**, 1.
20. F. A. FRENCH, E. J. BLANZ, JR., J. R. DO AMARAL and D. A. FAENCH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 1117.
21. Protocols for screening clinical agents and natural products against animal tumors and other biological systems, *Cancer Chemother. Rept.*, 1962, **25**, 1.